

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' MUSICAL ABILITIES THROUGH TYPES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL MUSICAL ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: this article covers the theoretical and practical basis for the formation of students' musical abilities based on the types of musical activity in the lessons of Primary School Music Culture. It also describes in detail about music creativity from the types of musical activities. The importance of music creativity activities "is also revealed in the lessons of Music Culture".

Keywords: music culture, primary education, music skills, skills, music creativity activities.

Activities such as the activity of music creativity in the process of music lessons, that is, the feeling of musical rhythm, the ability to tune in children's instruments, the performance of musical rhythmic movements, are also important for their physical development, as well as the development of musical abilities in students, mainly a sense of rhythm and method, and the skills. This is extremely necessary, especially for elementary school students. Because in the normative development of young children, any type of movement plays an important role. In this regard, there are great opportunities in the content of music lessons, and music lessons are also positively different from other disciplines in their characteristics.

Also, the Shetsarian pedagogue Emil Jacques-Dalkroz also emphasized this idea of feeling the rhythm - "...rhythm by performing movements, we prepare the Bolar for all art knowledge, since rhythm is the basis for all types of art - music, sculpture, architecture, poetry. In poetry, rhythm appears on the basis of sound. In poetry, rhythm is expressive in reading, in fine art, rhythm is the means of expression of a work of artistic art, which determines the specific theme of the structure of the work, serves to deeper reveal its ideological artistic aesthetic content.

We know that in all subjects, during classes, the teacher periodically takes into account the psyche of students and makes moving pauses, interrupting the course content and the thinking process of students.

Music lessons are an exception, since the types of musical movement - the character of the work being studied, are also important for a deep sense of artistic images, expressive and performance characteristics, as well as their

creative expression to some extent. That's when the lesson does not break from beginning to end and logically forms a whole.

The importance of movement suitable for music lies in the fact that students' sense of rhythm is activated, their movement is harmonized with the content of the music. The activity of musical creativity is also important for the education of the sense of metrorhythm, the development of lead and intonational skills. Because the development of metrorhythm is present in each type of activity of the lesson process. In addition, music creativity also plays a huge role in the development of creative activities in students.

Rhythm is one of the main sources, elements of music and is always necessary for the art of music. Rhythmic movement is the most convenient and expressive way of perceiving the duration of sound and its types. The importance of musical rhythmic movements in the development of all-round musical abilities of students is that students develop musical abilities, creative abilities, and skills of movement as a team are formed. Features of the performance of movement corresponding to music: the sense of rhythm is activated, the assimilation of musical material is deepened, the performance of movements helps to track the development of a musical image, qualities characteristic of the image of a musical work are formed.

Primary school students will have a thin voice apparatus, scattered attention, fussy, playful, memory, speech will not be fully developed but they will have the ability to clearly think, think. A dance suitable for music, performing game movements, helps students to concentrate, strengthen their memory and feel metrorhythm.

During the lesson, rhythmic movement exercises are used:

- ❖ *step, run, jump under marsh music;*
- ❖ *performing dance elements;*
- ❖ *familiar song, tattooing on the rhythmic pace of the melodies;*
- ❖ *conducting musical games;*
- ❖ *re-tattooing the rhythmic pace of the teacher's performance (with the help of applause or percussion instruments);*
- ❖ *expression of haracters (registers, triplets,) of music by hand and body movements;*
- ❖ *clap at the rhythmic pace of the example written on the board;*
- ❖ *clap the rhythmic samples given in the textbook or play in children's instruments;*
- ❖ *work with special cards on Note notes;*

- ❖ *articulating the rhythmic pace;*
- ❖ *rhythmic ostinato to the accompaniment of songs;*
- ❖ *reading and telling uncomplicated rhythmic partitures in percussion instruments;*
- ❖ *rhythmic dictations (playing the rhythmic pace of the recorded melody through applause or percussion instruments, etc.k.);*

All exercises are given in different sizes and tempos. National Music Culture dance art is also of great importance in the activities of music creativity. In the dance medium, students will be introduced to dance movements and music by national and fraternal peoples. Performing activities suitable for dance music students develop a worldview, musical memory, sense of rhythm and attention. Shevtsarian pedagogue Emil Jacques-Dalkroz stated that " ... the human body is an instrument of wisdom, beauty and purity " and that " before he starts playing music, he must learn to perceive and feel it with all your being, be watered with a feeling that creates rhythm and sounds", indicating that rhythmic movements and dance movements are important in kaydaraja.

Since primary school students do not fully master the notes and do not know their stretch, they have figurative "big" and "small" outlines. In the textbook, the rhythm of melodies is given in the form of large and small circles, and larger circles are performed in clapping or children's instruments in a way that is longer than small ones.

Performing movements to music activates a sense of rhythm in students. The musical material of the lesson is given to a deeper assimilation of yanda and enhances the emotional impact of music. Impressions of the forms of music, the patterns of musical development are strengthened with the help of rhythmic movements, a sense of rhythm is developed by changing the character and direction of movement.

Musical works, along with the development of musical – auditory soundtracks with the help of movements corresponding to the song, are also formed executive abilities, artistic tastes. If they are assigned the task of inventing an independent movement; they come up with and perform an action themselves, corresponding to the image, character of the music. Usually, programmatic music is selected for staging dances, since its content and sequence of movements become clear.

Also, the activity of the musical-rhythmic movement involves three runs among themselves:

1. It helps to develop such abilities as ensuring musical development, cultivating musical hearing, developing, forming skills to adapt movement to music, mastering musical knowledge; forming the skills to be able to subordinate movement to music

2. Movement skills are formed with the help of giving the right direction (marshona, shakhdam, trigger, calm, sporty, solemnity, sharp spring walking, etc.); stepping up (high, at the tip of the foot, wide, soft, springy, khorovodly, etc.); jumps (light, mobile); turns; hand movements (gentle, gentle, gentle, mobile); applause (slow, hard, low, high, with the hand shaking, holding close to each other, sliding "saucers", holding the palms sliding movements); dance elements (from Uzbek folk dances "mirror", "rope", "shoulder throw", "horse up the ball", hand movement if we look and to the side, dance elements similar to points, polka, golop, waltz, etc.); rotation at the tip of the foot, the combination of a jump with a springy step; hand movements (gentle, sharp); standing and changing in different situations; movement with objects includes execution (with balls, ribbons, flagella).

3. Students are focused on the formation of body movement management skills (precise and quick stop, movement change, etc.).

Together with the performance of rhythmic movements suitable for music, it helps students to open up their creative possibilities of playing musical instruments, develops the loudness of sound, introduces them to the sound of the orchestra and gives students a lot of joy. Because students are interested in the course process, perform with pleasure, feel the rhythm if we introduce instruments by singing live rather than showing them using visual aids.

At the same time, one of the types of activities is considered to be playing musical instruments in the primary class, playing as a team. The significance of this activity lies in the fact that it consists in the development of students' musical abilities, enrichment of their artistic skills, interest in performance activities and its development.

In music lessons, chivalrous and non-chivalrous instruments are used. Chanting instruments include metallophones and xylaphones; while non-chanting instruments include circles, simple shepherd spoons, small shouts, sapphires, drums, triangles, maracassa, and rumba.

In children's chogu, chicks are carried out in the same way as in the rabbit:

- listening to the melody, clapping and giving it a rhythmic tap;

- those who practice rhythmic tap to music will be taped in children's instruments, while those (passive) students who struggle to tap slowly will also be taught to perform together;
- students can exchange different instruments and use them to play music;
- students in the class are divided into 2 groups. Group 1 in applause and instruments. Group 2, on the other hand, can also carry out a method in sound (bum-bak, baka-baka-bum);
- playing depending on the rhythmic structures shown graphically in Instrumental Performance also increases, activates the creativity of students, comprehensively develops the skills of performance and musical abilities.

From the very first lessons, students will be taught the joint harmonious actions necessary for their participation in the ensemble when performing at Children's parties. For this purpose, a kind of "rhythmic orchestras" are created, in which students clap, tap the foot and play sticks, an empty or small stone, a box filled with chickpeas. Here, too, a different vote is formed.

If the palms are clapped in a howl, the sound will come out hard, muffled, and if the palms are in a flat state, the sound will come out clear and sonorous. With the extended or slightly bent fingers of one hand, it is possible to change the sound output by hitting the palm of the other hand. Taping is formed with the whole foot, with the tip of the foot, with the heel, with the turn of the foot and the heel, a sound is made by hitting the thigh with the palm, paws. All this, attracting students, allows you to correctly complete various rhythmic tasks and master the skills of playing a musical instrument.

In conclusion, it can be said that the activity of music creativity is of great importance in the formation of musical abilities in primary school students, such as the perception of music, the sense of rhythm, melodic and garmokin hearing, the perception of the form of music, musical memory, taste. As proof of these words, the method of the Swiss pedagogue Emil Jacques-Dalcrosis is based on the "development of musical hearing, memory, attention, sense of rhythm in students on the basis of specially selected exercises " in the formation of a sense of rhythm.

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